

The Effect Between Job Satisfaction, Work Stress, And Work Environment On Turnover Intention Mediated By Organizational Commitment To The Indonesian National Cyber And Crypto Agency

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: May 06 , 2021</p> <p>Accepted: October 08, 2021</p> <p>Keywords : Turnover Intention, Organizational Commitments, Job Satisfaction, Job Stressor, Job Environment</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5558002</p>	<p><i>This research aimed with analyzing the effect between job satisfaction, job stressor, and job environment against turnover intention mediated by organizational commitments in National Cyber And Crypto Agency and to provide suggestion as to how agency can reduce turnover intention rates through effective programs and policies. This independent variables are including job satisfaction (X1), job stressor (X2), and job environment (X3). For another one, de-pendent variable is turnover intention (Y) with intervening variable is organizational com-mitments (Z). The research approach for this research based on quantitative research such as interview, observation, and questionnaire. The model is analyzed by using statistics software of AMOS 24 version. Survey based data was collected 150 respondent. This study was founded that job satisfaction and job environment directly have positive and significant effect against organizational commitments. Job stressor directly has negative and significant effect against organizational commitments. Job satisfaction, job environment, and organizational commitments directly have negative and significant effect against turnover intention. Job stressor also has directly positive and significant effect against turnover intention. Job satisfaction and job environment negatively and significant effect to turn-over intention trough organizational commitments. Job stressor has positively and significant against turnover in-tention trough organizational commitments.</i></p>

Introduction

An existence of turnover intention is something that not desired by the organization. Turnover intention can be defined as the tendency or intention of employees to quit their job (Zeffane, 1994). Turnover can be in the form of resignation, transfer outside the organizational unit, dismissal or death an organization member. Turnover intention of employees in an organization cannot only occur in private organizations or organizations that are profit. It is possible that happen in government agencies. Although, the level of turnover intention in government agencies is not too high when compared to private profit organizations, the turnover can also have a negative impact on the organization. There are many causes for turnover intention, including work stress, work environment, job satisfaction, organizational commitment, and so on (Sutanto & Gunawan, 2015). According to Dharma (2013) said that, turnover intention has a negative impact on organizations because it creates instability in labor conditions, decreases employee productivity, a work atmosphere that is not conducive and also has an impact on increasing human resource costs.

The National Cyber and Crypto Agency (BSSN) is a government institution that under and responsible to the President, which has the task of implementing cyber security effectively and efficiently by utilizing, developing, and consolidating all elements related to cyber security. As a government institution that has the task of implementing cyber security in Indonesia, most of its employees are required to have a basic understanding on developments in information technology and information security. In meeting these needs, BSSN employees are recruited from several sources or through the recruitment of new employees based on the results of an analysis of human resource needs conducted by the Bureau of Organization and Human Resources.

There are employees who have graduated from the National Crypto Academy (AKSARA) and the State Code High School (STSN), to an existence of employees outside the structure who come from other government agencies. Where, a whole BSSN employees are dominated by graduates from AKSARA and STSN (Employee Dislocation 2019). As for AKSARA and STSN are official schools that coordinate directly under the Head of BSSN where the entire process of activities, from recruitment, education to competency development while working, is financed by the BSSN Budget Implementation List (DIPA). This is clearly a big investment in human resources, so there is a high turnover intention it will clearly have a negative impact on BSSN.

Based on data obtained from the Bureau of Organization and Human Resources, in the period from 2014-2018, the employee turnover rate has fluctuated.

Table 1. Data on employees leaving the BSSN agencies in 2014 - 2018

No	Year	Total of Employment (People)	Total of Resign (People)
1	2014	806	7
2	2015	891	12
3	2016	879	5
4	2017	870	24
5	2018	975	8
Total			56

Source: Documentation of the Bureau of Organization and Human Resources BSSN 2019

Based on a data, it can be seen that the total turnover of BSSN employees from 2014-2018 is 56 people. Where in 2017 is the highest employee turnover rate. This turnover also occurred due to several things, including because of the need to qualify for another government agency, choosing to move to another agency for personal reasons, and resigning or leaving a civil servant (PNS).

Indications of dissatisfaction, stress, and lack of commitment to the organization can be seen from the high intensity of employees who arrive late and do not enter the office without explanation. Harnoto (2002) stated that turnover intention is characterized by a decrease in the productivity level of employee performance at the company, usually this happens such as by often arriving late, often skipping classes, or having high levels of attendance for various reasons, lack of enthusiasm, and low initiative or lack of desire to trying better than he was in the early days of work. Based on data obtained from the Bureau of Organization and Human Resources, the level of employee tardiness has increased.

Table 2. Data on late employees and absent from office in 2019

No	Month	Total of Employment (People)	Delay (People)		No Absent (People)	
			Total	%	Total	%
1	January	968	392	40	370	38
2	Februari	1099	917	83	311	28
3	March	1099	879	80	340	31
4	April	1099	753	69	270	25
5	May	1099	703	64	272	25
6	June	1099	371	34	226	21
7	July	1099	750	68	299	27
8	August	1099	685	62	361	33
9	September	1099	565	51.4	267	24.3
10	October	1099	551	50.1	259	23.6
11	November	1099	514	46.8	255	23.2
Average			644	59.0	294	27.1

Source: Documentation of the Bureau of Organization and Human Resources BSSN 2019

Based on the data, it can be seen that the average BSSN employee who was late was 644 people or 59% and the average BSSN employee who did not attend was 294 people or 27.1% throughout 2019. Where a highest intensity of employees who were late occurred in the month February was 83%, while January was the highest intensity of absent employees at 38%. This is an indication of dissatisfaction, stress, and a lack of commitment to the organization.

In general, employees who are dissatisfied and have a turnover intention will leave their job (Miller et al., 2002). This is supported by several studies that have been conducted previously by (Sari, 2014), (Saeed et al., 2014), (Adeoye, 2016), (Ramalho Luz et al., 2018), (Saliem, 2018), (Sugiono, 2019)) and (Rijasawitri & Suana, 2020) regarding job satisfaction on turnover intention, where the results stated that job satisfaction has a negative and significant effect on turnover intention. This means that a higher of level for employee job satisfaction, the lower of an employee turnover intention will be. However, there are different results in the research conducted by (Setiyanto & Hidayat, 2017), where job satisfaction does not have a significant effect on turnover intention but organizational commitment has a significant effect on turnover intention. Research conducted by (Anisykurlilah, 2013) also shown that job satisfaction has no effect on organizational commitment. As well as research conducted by (Adawiyah, 2019) which shown that job satisfaction does not have a significant effect on turnover intention.

(Moore, 2000) stated that job stressors and a lack of job satisfaction, which are factors that can lead to a person's desire to leave their job. This is supported by several studies that have been conducted previously by (Sari, 2014), (Saliem, 2018), and (Rijasawitri & Suana, 2020) regarding work stress on turnover intention, where the results stated that work stress has a positive and significant effect on turnover intention. This means that the higher level of employee work stress and also the higher level of turnover intention. However, there are different results in the research conducted by (Agustina, 2013), which shown that job stress does not have a significant effect on employee turnover. Research conducted by (Hakim, 2017) also shows that work stress does not have a significant effect on organizational commitment. So, research conducted by (Arliansyah, 2016), where the work environment and work stress do not significantly influence turnover intention.

(Mobley, 2011) stated that the factors has an influence a person to move are determined by individual factors, which is the work environment. This is supported by research that has been previously by (Rijasawitri & Suana, 2020) regarding the effect between a non-physical work environment and turnover intention, where the result stated that the non-physical work environment has a negative effect on turnover intention. This means are more better than the work environment, also the lower on turnover intention will be. However, there are different results in the research conducted by (Setiawan & Lestari, 2016), where the work environment does not have a positive and significant effect on organizational commitment. (Arliansyah, 2016) also stated different research results where work environment and work stress did not significantly influence turnover intention.

According to (Griffeth et al., 2000) that almost all turnover intention models are caused by low levels of job satisfaction and organizational commitment. This is supported by previous research on organizational commitment to turnover intention by (Sari, 2014), (Ramalho Luz et al., 2018), (Saliem, 2018), and (Sugiono, 2019) where organizational commitment has a negative and significant on turnover intention. This means that the higher the level of organizational commitment an employee has, the lower of employee turnover intention will be. Meanwhile, the results of previous research conducted by (Saeed et al., 2014) shown that different research results, such the insignificant influence between organizational commitment and turnover intention. Moreover, research conducted by (Mandeno, 2017) also shown that organizational commitment has no significant effect on turnover intention.

Based on previous research, there are several research gaps on job satisfaction, work stress and work environment that affect to turnover intention, shown that different research findings from one researcher to another. So, for further research is needed and expected to clarify how the effect of satisfaction work, work stress, and work environment on turnover intention. This study was developed to fill previous research gaps by using the variables of job satisfaction, work stress, and work environment as exogenous independent variables that affect organizational commitment as an intervening variable and turnover intention as an endogenous dependent variable.

The purpose was to analyze the effect of job satisfaction, job stress, and work environment on turnover intention mediated by organizational commitment at the National Cyber and Crypto Agency. Besides being able to provide new empirical evidence, this study can contribute to covering the gap between the results of previous studies. From a practical point of view, this research can be used as material for policy considerations in dealing with and understanding the problem of employee turnover at the National Cyber and Crypto Agency which can affect organizational effectiveness.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Turnover Intention

Intention is the intention or desire that arises in an individual to do something. Meanwhile, turnover is the cessation or withdrawal of an employee from the workplace. Thus, turnover intentions are the tendency or intention of employees to stop working from their jobs (Zeffane, 1994). (Abelson, 2009) explained that the desire to move reflects to the desire of individuals to leave the organization and look for other work alternatives. In the research conducted, this variable is used in a broad scope covering all organizational withdrawals carried out by employees. The indicators used in this study adopted by the theory put forward by (Abelson, 2009), where turnover intention can be measured through: 1) An existence of thoughts of leaving; 2) The desire to find other job vacancies; 3) Evaluating the possibility of finding a decent job elsewhere; and 4) There are better opportunities elsewhere.

Job Satisfaction

Job satisfaction is a pleasant emotional attitude and loves his job (Malayu S.P Hasibuan, 2012). This attitude was reflected by work morale, discipline, and work performance. Job satisfaction is enjoyed at work, outside work, and a combination of inside and outside work. The indicators also used in this study are adopted from the theory put forward by (Luthans, 2005) in his book organizational behavior, which is a development of the three previous dimensions, such as the work itself, salary, promotion opportunities, supervision, and colleagues.

Job Stress

(Mangkunegara, 2011) stated that work stress is a feeling for presses or feels depressed with experienced by employees in facing work. This work stress can cause unstable emotions, feelings of uneasiness, likes to be alone, has difficulty sleeping, excessive smoking, cannot relax, is anxious, tense, nervous, increases blood pressure and experiences digestive disorders. (Robbins & Judge, 2009) defined for stress as a response to adaptation and influenced by individual differences and psychological processes, as a consequence of action. (Handoko, 2011) suggested that a stress is like condition of tension that can affect one's emotions, thought processes and emotional conditions. Work stress can be measured through 4 (four) indicators (Mangkunegara, 2009) including workload, working time, feedback received, and responsibility.

Work Environment

NitiseMITO (2001) argued that the work environment also everything around any workers, which can influence them in carrying out their assigned tasks. Meanwhile, Sedarmayanti (2016) explained that the work environment is an entire tooling tool and materials faced, the surrounding environment where a person works, his work methods, and work arrangements both as individuals and as groups. The indicators were adapted from the theory by Soetjipto (2009) including physical dimensions are measured using 6 (six) indicators, such as lighting, air circulation, noise, color, air humidity, and facilities. Non-physical dimensions are measured using 3 (three) indicators such as harmonious relationship, opportunities for advancement, and security at work.

Organizational Commitment

The definition of commitment refers to loyalty, which commitment is defined as the relative strength of individual identification and involvement to a particular organization (Armstrong, 2006). Kiesler and Sakumura as quoted by Salancik (2005) defined that commitment as a bond between individuals and behavioral actions. Even when commitment is defined as an intellectual characteristic, personal traits such as honesty cannot be mandated or enforced from without (Brown et al., 2004). In short, it is said that employees' interest in the organization is built and maintained on the basis of their willingness to give and receive competitive advantages from both parties. There are several things that are indicators of employee organizational commitment. According to Luthans (2006) said that an organizational commitment is multidimensional, so there is a development of support for the three component models proposed by (Meyer & Allen, 1993). These indicators are affective commitment with the employee's emotional attachment, identification, and involvement in the organization. Continuous commitment is a commitment based on losses associated with leaving employees from the organization. Normative commitment is a feeling of obligation to remain in the organization because it has to be, so it can action to the right thing to do.

Job Satisfaction and Organizational Commitment

Job satisfaction is a pleasant emotional attitude and loves his job (Hasibuan, 2017). Greenberg & Baron (2003) stated that job satisfaction reflects individual awareness, pleasure and reactions to individual assessments of their work. Meanwhile, Sutrisno (2010) in his book states the opinion of Yulk and Wexly, that job satisfaction is a person's feelings about his job. More broadly the definition of job satisfaction as expressed. Luthans (2005) can be said to be a pleasant feeling or positive emotion that arises from the person's assessment of his job or the experience he feels at work. In line with the opinion above, Hellriegel and Slocurn (2004) define feelings that reflect attitudes toward work. Job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on organizational commitment (Hidayat, 2015). Handoko (2011) and Mathis & Jackson (2012) also stated that job satisfaction reflects a person's feelings towards their job, when someone is satisfied with their work they will be more committed to the organization. Based on the theory and previous research that has been mentioned above, the hypotheses proposed in this study are:

Job Stress and Organizational Commitment

Mangkunegara (2009) stated that work stress is a feeling that presses or feels depressed experienced by employees in facing work. Robbins & Judge (2009) defines stress as a response in adjustment, which is influenced by individual differences and psychological processes, as a consequence of action. Handoko (2011) suggests stress as a condition of tension that can affect one's emotions, thought processes, and emotional conditions. Job stress has an effect on decreasing organizational commitment. Job stress is negatively related to organizational commitment where employees who have high levels of stress have implications for low organizational commitment (Cha et al., 2011), (Pool, 2000), (Velnampy, 2009).

Work Environment and Organizational Commitment

Nitisemito (2001) argued that the work environment is everything around the workers that can influence them in carrying out their assigned tasks. Meanwhile, Sedarmayanti (2016) explained that the work environment is an entire tooling tool and materials faced, also surrounding environment where a person works, his work methods, and work arrangements both as individuals and as groups. The work environment has a positive and significant influence on organizational commitment (Hanaysha, 2016). According to Danish et al. (2013) said that the work environment is a very important factor with affect between job satisfaction and employee commitment in an institution or organization.

Job Satisfaction and Turnover Intention

Job satisfaction is a pleasant emotional attitude and loves his job (Hasibuan, 2006). Greenverg and Baron (2003) stated that job satisfaction reflects individual awareness, pleasure and reactions to individual assessments of their work. Meanwhile, Sutrisno (2010) in his book stated the opinion of Yulk and Wexly, that job satisfaction is a person's feelings about his job. More broadly, the notion of job satisfaction as expressed by Luthan (2008) can be said to be a pleasant feeling or a person's positive emotions that arise from the person's assessment of his job or the experience he feels at work. In line with the opinion above, Hellriegel and Slocurn (2004) define feelings that reflect attitudes toward work. Job satisfaction has a negative and significant effect on turnover intention (Mathis and Jackson, 2001). The results of research conducted by Rijasawitri & Suana (2020) stated that workforce turnover is related to job dissatisfaction. The higher a person's job satisfaction level, the lower the intensity to leave his job.

Job Stress and Turnover Intention

Mangkunegara (2000) stated that job stress is a feeling that presses or feels depressed experienced by employees in facing work. Robbins (2006) defined for stress as a response to adaptation that is influenced by individual differences and psychological processes, as a consequence of action. Handoko (2001) suggested that stress as a condition of tension and can affect one's emotions, thought processes, and emotional conditions. Research conducted by Rismawan et al. (2014) founded that job stress has a positive and significant effect on turnover intention. Other research also stated that job stress also has a significant effect on the desire of employees to leave the organization (Anggraini, 2013).

Work Environment and Turnover Intention

Nitisemito (2010) stated that a work environment is everything around the workers that can influence them in carrying out their assigned duties. Meanwhile, Sedarmayanti (2009) explained that a work environment is the whole tooling tool and material faced, like surrounding environment where a person works, his work methods, and work arrangements both as individuals and as groups. The work environment has a negative relationship with turn-over intention, which shown that good working conditions can reduce the number of turnover intention. The work environment has a negative and significant effect on turnover intention (Dwiningtyas, 2015) and (Qureshi et al., 2013).

Organizational Commitment and Turnover Intention

Steers et al. (2013) defined that an organizational commitment as a sense of identification (trust in organizational values), involvement and loyalty, which is expressed by an employee towards the organization. Organizational commitment is a condition in which employees like the organization and are willing to put forth a high level of effort for the benefit of the organization and the achievement of its organizational goals. Mowday (1998) defined that commitment as the relative strength of an individual's identification with and involvement in a particular organization, which is characterized by a belief in the goals and values of the organization, a willingness to exert effort on behalf of the organization and a strong desire to remain with the organization. Organizational commitment likes a partnership and employee loyalty to the organizational goals. Morrison (1997) stated that commitment is an important factor for organizations because of its effect on turnover and its relationship with performance, which assumes that committed individuals tend to develop greater efforts at their jobs. This is supported by several studies, which stated that employee commitment to the organization will make employees loyal to the organization and work well for the benefit of the organization (Yuwaliatin, 2006). The results of research in the journal Salleh et al. (2012) founded that organizational commitment has a negative and significant effect on turnover intention. Employee commitment to the organization will make employees loyal to the organization and work well for the benefit of the organization (Yuwaliatin, 2006).

Job Satisfaction, Turnover Intention, and Organizational Commitment

Job satisfaction and organizational commitment tend to influence each other. People who are relatively satisfied with their work will be more committed to the organization, and people who are committed to the organization are more likely to get greater job satisfaction (Mathis & Jackson, 2012). According to Pepe (2010) said that an existence on a high work supervision, organizational commitment (affective and continuous), and job satisfaction will cause the desire of employees to leave the organization to be reduced. The results of research conducted by Anari (2012) shown that there is a significant positive relationship between job satisfaction and organizational commitment. The same result is also stated in Ismail's (2016) research, that job satisfaction significantly affects to organizational commitment. The results of research conducted by Salleh et al. (2012) stated that there is a negative and significant relationship between job satisfaction and the desire to change jobs, and also founded that organizational commitment has a negative and significant relationship with the desire to change jobs. The conclusion from the research of Sow et al. (2015) also showed a negative and significant relationship between affective commitment and turnover intention.

Job Stress, Turnover Intention, and Organizational Commitment

Employees who have work stress will have an impact on low organizational commitment, so that the higher work stress experienced by employees, the organizational commitment will decrease (Caesarani & Riana, 2016). The role of conflict as a form of stress has an effect on decreasing organizational commitment, which means that there is a negative relationship between work stress and organizational commitment (Pool, 2000). Research results from Ruzungunde et al. (2016) and Bhatti et al. (2016) founded that job stress has a negative effect on organizational commitment. Meanwhile, the results of research conducted by Arshadi & Damiri (2013) shown that there is a positive relationship between work stress and turnover intention. Job stress has a positive effect on turnover intention (Sewwandi & Perere, 2016).

Work Environment, Turnover Intention, and Organizational Commitment

According to Alvina (2018) discussed that more better any work environment in the company, than a higher on organizational commitment, and vice versa, the more employees feel that the company's work environment is not good, their commitment to the company will decrease. The work environment is a very important factor and can affect to job satisfaction, then employee commitment in an institution or organization (Hanaysha, 2016). The results of the study founded that work environment and organizational commitment have a positive and significant relationship (Vanaki & Vagharseyyedin, 2009). There is a strong relationship between work environment and organizational commitment (Cheng & Kadir, 2018). While, the results of research conducted by Lee et al. (2016) shown that the work environment has a negative and significant effect on turnover intention. The same research results were also stated by Wan et al. (2018) that there is a negative influence between work environment and turnover intention.

METHODOLOGY

Sample Procedure

The sampling method used in this study was accidental sampling. This method is classified as a non-probability sampling method because not every employee who works in this organization, which has the same opportunity to become respondents in this study. The minimum number of samples in the study is 23 indicators \times 5 = 115 people. The sample was used by researchers as many as 150 people, which has met the minimum number of samples needed. As many as 63.4% of respondents were male, 54.1% of respondents had an age of 21-30 years, 69.2% of respondents with an under-graduate education level, 54.2% for respondents held executive positions, 95.8% for respondents had the rank /goal. III, 39.9% for respondents with a working period of 1 - 5 years, and as much as 34.2% for respondents came from the Main Secretariat of the BSSN work unit.

Measurement

This study was uses a five-item scale developed by Sugiyono (2015). The rating scale ranges from 1 = "strongly disagree" to 5 = "strongly agree". An example item is "the salary I receive is in accordance with the results of the work I give to the organization".

The turnover intention indicator also used in this study adopted with the theory put forward by (Abelson, 2009), where turnover intention can be measured by an existence of thoughts to leaving, a desire to find other job vacancies, evaluating the possibility of finding a decent job elsewhere, and there are better opportunities elsewhere. Job satisfaction indicators are used in this study adopted by the theory put forward by (Luthans, 2005) in his book organizational behavior, which is a development of the previous three dimensions, such as the job itself, salary, promotion opportunities, supervision, and colleagues. Work stress can be measured through 4 (four) indicators (Mangkunegara, 2009) including workload, working time, feedback received, and responsibility.

Method of Analysis

The analytical method used in this research is a quantitative analysis method using the Structural Equation Model (SEM) through the AMOS version 24 software.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Analysis Model Structural

Analysis of the results of data processing at the full model SEM stage was carried out by performing a suitability test and statistical test. The following is the full model result of the study using SEM which is shown in Figure 1.

Picture 1. SEM Full Model

The results of the suitability test (Goodness of fit) shown that the full model has a good goodness of fit with a calculated Chi Square value smaller than the chi square table in good fit results. Whereas the probability, RMSEA, RMR, TLI, CFI, PNFI, and PGFI are also in good fit results.

DISCUSSION

Hypothesis testing

The relationship between constructs in the hypothesis is shown by the regression weight values (Hair et al., 2010). Hypothesis testing is conducted to determine whether the independent variable affects the dependent variable or not. The hypothesis is accepted if the value of prob (P) < 0.05 or CR > 1.96 (critical Z value for 95% confidence degree).

Table 3. Regression Weights

		Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Lable
Organization commitment	<--- Work Satisfaction	.646	.140	4.606	***	par_24
Organization commitment	<--- Work Environment	.259	.066	3.943	***	par_27
Organization commitment	<--- Job Stress	-.234	.081	-2.889	.004	par_28
Turnover_Intention	<--- Organization commitment	-.436	.131	-3.339	***	par_22
Turnover_Intention	<--- Work Satisfaction	-.628	.172	-3.654	***	par_23
Turnover_Intention	<--- Job Stress	.262	.091	2.868	.004	par_25
Turnover_Intention	<--- Work Environment	-.173	.075	-2.314	.021	par_26

Table 4. Standardized Regression Weights

			Estimate
Organization commitment	<-- -	Work Satisfaction	.417
Organization commitment	<-- -	Work Environment	.319
Organization commitment	<-- -	Job Stress	-.236
Turnover_Intention	<-- -	Organization commitment	-.343
Turnover_Intention	<-- -	Work Satisfaction	-.319
Turnover_Intention	<-- -	Job Stress	.208
Turnover_Intention	<-- -	Work Environment	-.168

Source: Data processed by AMOS (2020)

Mediation Test (Sobel Test)

The Sobel test serves to determine whether or not there is an indirect effect of the independent variable on the dependent variable through the intervening variable. In addition, a Sobel test is used to test the ability of the intervening variable to become a mediator in the research framework model. The calculation of the single test uses the following formula (Ghozali, 2017):

$$sab = \sqrt{b^2sa^2 + a^2sb^2 + sa^2sb^2}$$

$$t = \frac{ab}{sab}$$

Information :

sab = magnitude on direct effect to the standard error

a = independent variable path with intervening variables

b = path of intervening variable with the dependent variable

sa = standard error of the coefficient a

sb = standard error coefficient b

If the t value > t table value, it can be concluded that there is a mediating effect. By using the formula above, the following results are obtained:

Table 5. Sobel Test

No	Path	Unstandardized Coefficient	Standard Error	Sobel Test Results		
				t-stat		
1	KK - KO	0.646	0.140	t-stat	-2.699	p*=0.006
	KO - TI	-0.436	0.131	Conclusion	Significant	

2	SK - KO	-0.234	0.081	t-stat	2.182	p*=0.029
	KO - TI	-0.436	0.131	Conclusion	Significant	
3	LK - KO	0.259	0.066	t-stat	-2.538	p*=0.011
	KO - TI	-0.436	0.131	Conclusion	Significant	

Source: Data processed (2020)

The Effect Between Job Satisfaction and Organizational Commitment

This test stated that job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on organizational commitment, this is evidenced by the CR value of 4.606 and a significance value of 0.001. It can be concluded that the higher job satisfaction, the stronger organizational commitment will be and vice versa. This means that the organizational commitment of BSSN employees is influenced by the job satisfaction they feel. So, it can be concluded that job satisfaction directly has a positive and significant effect on organizational commitment.

This research is relevant to the statements of Handoko (2001), Mathis and Jackson (2011) discussed that job satisfaction reflects to a person's feelings towards their job, when someone is satisfied with their work they will be more committed to the organization. The results of this study are in line with previous research conducted by Nahid Naderi Anari (2012) which shown that there is a significant positive relationship between job satisfaction and organizational commitment. Then research from Azman Ismail (2016) also founded that job satisfaction significantly affects to organizational commitment.

Based on the results of respondents' perceptions, the highest average of the job satisfaction variables is found in the satisfaction indicator for coworkers. BSSN employees stated that they were more satisfied with colleagues who had the desire to cooperate openly and shoulder to shoulder. They are feel like a comfortable working relationship between employees will increase their commitment to the organization. As well as BSSN employees stated that they can contribute to each other between colleagues. This indicates has any efforts to increase employee job satisfaction at BSSN and it will have an impact on increasing employee organizational commitment. In determining organizational policies, it is necessary to prioritize the fulfillment of needs in terms of increasing job satisfaction for employees which will have an impact on increasing organizational commitment.

The Effect Between Job Stress and Organizational Commitment

This test states that work stress has a negative and significant effect on organizational commitment, this is evidenced by the CR value of -2.889 and a significance value of 0.004. It can be concluded that the higher level of stress at work, also the lower on organizational commitment will be and vice versa. This means that the organizational commitment of BSSN employees is influenced by the level of stress at work. So, it can be concluded that job stress directly has a negative and significant effect on organizational commitment. The results of this study are in line with previous research conducted by Mizbah Hayat Bhatti, et al., (2016) which shown that there is a negative relationship between work stress and organizational commitment. Research from Vongai Sarah Ruzungunde, et al., (2016) also agrees that work stress has a negative effect on organizational commitment for employees who work in health institutions.

Based on the results of respondents' perceptions, the highest average of the work stress variable is the stress indicator on responsibility. This reason is based on the feeling of stress of BSSN employees at work when ordered by their superiors to do work, which is not their responsibility. BSSN employees also feel like a high pressure from their superiors at work. An existence of excessive delegation on authority, which is not in accordance with the proportion on the organization. There is also felt by employees as a cause of stress. As well as BSSN employees have a job that has a high risk of employee safety and comfort, which also causes stress for employees. This indicated that efforts to deal with work stress of employees at BSSN will have an impact on increasing employee organizational commitment. So, in determining the next strategy it is necessary to reconsider the work stress management mechanism such as providing equal opportunities for all employees to get work guidance services.

The Effect Between Work Environment and Organizational Commitment

This test stated that the work environment has a positive and significant influence on organizational commitment, this is evidenced by the CR value of 3.943 and a significance value of 0.001. It can be concluded that more better a good work environment, than also stronger the organizational commitment will be and vice versa. This means that the organizational commitment of BSSN employees is influenced by the existing work environment. So, it can be concluded that the work environment directly has a positive and significant effect on organizational commitment.

The results are in line with previous research conducted by Ng Pek Cheng and Suhaida A. Kadir (2018) where the results of the study indicated that there is a strong relationship between work environment and organizational commitment. Meanwhile, the results of research from Zohreh Vanaki and Seyyed A. Vagharseyyedin (2009) founded that work environment and organizational commitment have a positive and significant relationship.

Based on the results of respondents' perceptions, the highest average of the work environment variables is the lighting indicator. Employees want a work environment is comfortable with a bright and not dim atmosphere. When working comfortably, they will feel for the commitment employees to the organization will increase. This indicates like any efforts to improve the work environment of employees at BSSN will have an impact on increasing employee organizational commitment. Moreover, it is necessary to improve policies from BSSN to develop and renew the work environment so that employee commitment can increase.

The Effect Between Job Satisfaction and Turnover Intention

This test stated that job satisfaction has a negative and significant effect on turnover intention, this is evidenced by the CR value of -3.654 and a significance value of 0.001. It can be concluded that the higher job satisfaction, so the lower turnover intention will be and vice versa. This means that the turnover intention of BSSN employees is influenced by the job satisfaction they feel. In this case, it can be concluded that job satisfaction directly has a negative and significant effect on turnover intention.

The results of the analysis are supported by the expert's definition as stated by Robbins (2001: 179) "Job satisfaction is negatively associated with the desire to leave employees (Turnover Intention) from the company." Robbins' opinion above is supported by several studied that have been previously by Saliem (2018), Sugiono et al. (2019) and Rijasawitri et al. (2020) regarding job satisfaction on turnover intention, where the results stated that a job satisfaction has a negative and significant effect on turnover intention.

Based on the results of respondents' perceptions, the highest average of the job satisfaction variables is found in the satisfaction indicator for coworkers. BSSN employees stated that they were more satisfied with colleagues who had the desire to cooperate openly and shoulder to shoulder. They are feel such a comfortable working relationship between employees will increase their commitment to the organization. As well as BSSN employees stated that they can contribute to each other between colleagues. This also indicated that efforts to increase employee job satisfaction at BSSN will have an impact on reducing employee turnover intention. BSSN must be consistent in encouraging increased by organizational commitment and emphasizing employee turnover intention with commitment and serious organizational steps in providing job satisfaction. So, the form of promotion is in accordance with the system and rules for BSSN employees in the form of career pattern guidelines and policies.

The Effect Between Job Stress and Turnover Intention

This test stated that job stress has a positive and significant effect on turnover intention, this is evidenced by the CR value of 2.868 and a significance value of 0.004. It can be concluded that the higher the level of stress at work, the higher the turnover intention will be and vice versa. This means that the turnover intention of BSSN employees is influenced by the level of stress at work. Additionally, it can be concluded that job stress directly has a positive and significant effect on turnover intention.

The results are in line with previous research conducted by Nasrin Arshadi and Hojat Damiri (2013) where the results of the study indicated that there is a positive relationship between work stress and turnover intention. Likewise the research results from Sewwandi, D.V.S. and Perere, G.D.N. (2016) founded that there was a positive influence between job stress and turnover intention.

Based on the results of respondents' perceptions, the highest average of the work stress variable is the stress indicator on responsibility. This reason is based on the feeling of stress of BSSN employees at work when

ordered by their superiors to do work, which is not their responsibility. BSSN employees also feel the high pressure from their superiors at work. An existence of excessive delegation of authority, which is not in accordance with a proportion of the organization also felt by employees as a cause of stress. As well as BSSN employees have a job that has a high risk of employee safety and comfort, which also causes stress for employees. This indicates that any efforts to reduce employee work stress at BSSN will have an impact on reducing employee turnover intention. The policies can be carried out by BSSN in this case, like by providing an even workload and in accordance with the competencies possessed by employees will be able to encourage increased performance. So, it can have an impact on increasing organizational commitment and reducing employee turnover intention.

The Effect Between Work Environment and Turnover Intention

This test stated that the work environment has a negative and significant effect on turnover intention, this is evidenced by the CR value of -2.314 and a significance value of 0.002. It can be concluded that the better the work environment, the lower turnover intention will be and vice versa. This means that the turnover intention of BSSN employees is influenced by the existing work environment. So, it can be concluded by the work environment has a negative and insignificant effect directly on turnover intention.

The results are supported by the definition of an expert as stated by Mobley (2011) which stated that the factors that influence a person to move are determined by individual factors, which is the work environment. Mobley's opinion above is supported by several studies that have been conducted previously by Byoung Kwon Lee, et al. (2016) which resulted that the work environment has a negative and significant effect on turnover intention. Qiaoqin Wan, et al., (2018) also stated that there is a negative influence between work environment and turnover intention based on the results of their research.

Based on the results of respondents' perceptions, the highest average of the work environment variables is the lighting indicator. Employees want a work environment is comfortable with a bright and not dim atmosphere. When working comfortably, they will felt that the commitment that employees have to the organization will increase. So, they will have more loyalty to the organization. This efforts can improve the work environment of employees at BSSN will have an impact on reducing employee turnover intention. Some form of efforts to improve the work environment that can be carried out by BSSN. There is a needed to pay attention to the management in work space by providing a comfortable work environment. So, some employees can concentrate more while working, so that employee performance will increase.

The Effect Between Organizational Commitment and Turnover Intention

This test stated that organizational commitment has a negative and significant effect on turnover intention, this is evidenced by a CR value of -3.339 and a significance value of 0.001. It can be concluded that the higher or stronger the organizational commitment, the lower turnover intention will be and vice versa. This means that the turnover intention of BSSN employees is influenced by employee commitment to the organization. So, it can be concluded that organizational commitment directly has a negative and significant effect on turnover intention.

From these results, it can be concluded that the research is in line with the research of Sow et al. (2015) who founded that a negative and significant relationship between organizational commitment, especially affective commitment and turnover intention. This result is also confirmed by research from Salleh et al. (2012) which stated that there is a significant negative relationship between organizational commitment and the desire to change jobs. In addition, research from Pepe (2010) stated that organizational employee commitment (affective and continuous) will make employees' intention to leave the organization significantly reduced.

Based on the results of respondents' perceptions, the highest average of the organizational commitment variable is found in the normative commitment indicator. BSSN employees stated that they have made commitments in the form of continuing to carry out work assignments anytime and anywhere, and also provide benefits from study assignments given by the BSSN office by applying them in the field of work. This efforts to increase employee organizational commitment at BSSN will have an impact on reducing employee turnover intention. Some of the commitment efforts have been made by BSSN employees include doing the job optimally even though there is no interest, working sincerely and wholeheartedly, and always trying to complete the job whatever the demands, where these things can make BSSN employees have the desire to continue to perform at BSSN, so it will minimize employee turnover intention.

The Effect Between Job Satisfaction and Turnover Intention through Organizational Commitment

The results showed that the independent variable job satisfaction, also could explain the dependent variable (turnover intention) through organizational commitment with a t-calculated value of -2.699 (-2.699 lower than -

1.96). So, it can be concluded that job satisfaction has a negative and significant effect on turnover intention through organizational commitment. In direct and indirect relationships, a job satisfaction variable has highest value with the total effect value of 0.417 and -0.463. This job satisfaction variable has a high influence on organizational commitment and employee turnover intention. In determining organizational policies, it is necessary to prioritize the fulfillment of needs in terms of increasing job satisfaction for employees which will have an impact on increasing organizational commitment and suppressing the level of turnover intention.

The results are also reinforced by research from Edi Sugiono and Anggun Diah Safitri (2019) suggested that based on the results of hypothesis testing using structural equation modeling or SEM (Structural Equation Modeling) proved by a job satisfaction, organizational commitment, and organizational culture. This has a negative influence and significant on turnover intention, a job insecurity has a positive and significant effect on turnover intention, and organizational commitment mediates the relationship between job insecurity, job satisfaction, and organizational culture to turnover intention.

From the results of hypothesis testing, a path coefficient value on the variable of job satisfaction on turnover intention is 0.319. After being mediated by the organizational commitment variable, the path coefficient value of the job satisfaction variable on turnover intention became 0.309. There is a difference in the amount of coefficient on variable path for a job satisfaction on turnover intention of 0.01. In this case, the organizational commitment variable has not played a full role in providing mediation to increase the effect between a job satisfaction variables and turnover intention. So, this is also supported by the results on the calculation about the indirect effect using calculations of the value of the Variance Accounted For (VAF) variable of job satisfaction on turnover intention through organizational commitment of 0.309, which is included in the partial mediation category. This efforts also can increase employee job satisfaction at BSSN, will have an impact on reducing employee turnover intention through increased organizational commitment. So, in carrying out its duties and functions properly, every policy issued by the BSSN organization in order to suppress employee turnover intention must pay attention to efforts to increase job satisfaction for employees and employee organizational commitment.

Based on the results, a job satisfaction on turnover intention, it was founded that job satisfaction does not have a significant effect on turnover intention, but organizational commitment has a significant effect on turnover intention (Setiyanto et al., 2017), job satisfaction has no effect on organizational commitment. (Anisykurillillah et al., 2013) said that a job satisfaction does not have a significant effect on turnover intention (Adawiyah, 2019). Through this research, it was founded that job satisfaction has a negative and significant effect on turnover intention through the organizational commitment variable as a mediating variable. This means that the organizational commitment variable is able to act as a mediating variable with a partial level of mediation. The novelty of this research can be proven by an existence on organizational commitment variable, which is able to fill the previous research gap.

The Effect Between Job Stress and Turnover Intention through Organizational Commitment

The results were showed that the work stress-free variable in this study could explain the dependent variable like turnover intention through organizational commitment with a t-calculated value of 2.182 (2.182 greater than 1.96). So, it can be concluded that job stress has a positive and significant effect on turnover intention through organizational commitment.

The results were also reinforced by research from Rizal Miftachus Saliem (2018), which is any hypothesis testing using path analysis proved by a job satisfaction and job stress have a positive effect on organizational commitment, a job stress has an effect on turnover intention, and a job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on turnover intention through organizational commitment.

From the results of hypothesis testing, a coefficient value for variable path on work stress on turnover intention is 0.208. After being mediated by the organizational commitment variable, the path coefficient value of the work stress variable on turnover intention becomes 0.280. There is an increase in the coefficient of work stress variable on turnover intention by 0.072. In this case, the organizational commitment variable plays a role in providing mediation to increase the influence between job stress variables on turnover intention. This is also supported by the calculation of the indirect effect using calculations, the value of the Variance Accounted For (VAF) variable of work stress on turnover intention through organizational commitment of 0.280, which is included in the partial mediation category. This means that the variable organizational commitment can mediate the effect of job stress on turnover intention.

This efforts can reduce employee work stress at BSSN will have an impact on reducing employee turnover intention through increased organizational commitment. This BSSN organization must be consistent in managing employee stress in order to increase organizational commitment and reduce employee turnover intention. So, in determining the next strategy has necessary to reconsider the work stress management mechanism such as providing equal opportunities for all employees to get work guidance services.

Based on the results were regarding work stress on turnover intention, it was founded that work stress did not have a significant effect on employee turnover (Agustina, 2013), job stress did not have a significant effect on organizational commitment (Hakim, 2017), and job stress does not have a significant effect on turnover intention (Arliansyah, 2016). Through this research, it is founded that job stress has a positive and significant effect on turnover intention through an organizational commitment variable as a mediating variable. This organizational commitment variable is able to act as a mediating variable with a partial level of mediation. The novelty can be proven by an existence for organizational commitment variable, which is able to fill the previous research gap.

The Effect Between Work Environment and Turnover Intention through Organizational Commitment

The results showed that a work environment could explained with turnover intention through organizational commitment with a t value of -2.538 (-2.538 lower than -1.96). So, it can be concluded that the work environment has a negative and significant effect on turnover intention through organizational commitment.

The results also supported by the definition of an expert as stated by Sutanto and Gunawan (2013) which stated that any causes of turnover intention include work stress, work environment, job satisfaction, organizational commitment, and so on. This opinion is supported by research that has been done previously by Rijasawitri et al. (2020) regarding the effect of a non-physical work environment on turnover intention, where the result states that a non-physical work environment has a negative effect on turnover intention. This means that the higher a work environment with the lower of turnover intention will be.

From the results of hypothesis testing, the coefficient value of the work environment variable on turnover intention is 0.168. After being mediated by the organizational commitment variable, the path coefficient value of the work environment variable on turnover intention becomes 0.395. There is an increase in the coefficient of work environment variable on turnover intention of 0.227. In this case, the organizational commitment variable plays a role in providing mediation to increase the effect between work environment variables on turnover intention. This is also supported by the results of the calculation of the indirect effect using calculations, the value of the Variance Accounted For (VAF) work environment variable on turnover intention through organizational commitment of 0.395, which is included in the partial mediation category. This organizational commitment variable can mediate the effect between the work environment and turnover intention.

This indicates that efforts to improve any work environment from employees at BSSN, and will have an impact on reducing employee turnover intention through increased organizational commitment. The commitment of employee organization at BSSN can increase when there is a work environment that respects each other's main duties and functions, a professional work environment without conflicts of interest, communicative between employees, and superiors and fellow employees, moreover bureaucracy is not rigid, and minimizes seniority relations at work.

Based on the results, any work environment on turnover intention, it was founded that the work environment did not have a positive and significant effect on organizational commitment (Setiawan et al., 2016) and the work environment did not significantly influence turnover intention (Arliansyah, 2016) . Through this research, it is the work environment has a negative and significant effect on turnover intention through the organizational commitment variable as a mediating variable. This organizational commitment variable is able to act as a mediating variable with a partial level of mediation. Additionally, a novelty for this research can be proven by an existence of the organizational commitment variable, which is able to fill the previous research gap.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusion

Based on the results are proving the hypothesis through some research procedures, which have been carried out, job satisfaction, and work environment, respectively, have a positive and significant effect on organizational commitment. Job stress directly has a negative and significant effect on organizational commitment. Job satisfaction, work environment, and organizational commitment, respectively, have a negative and significant

effect on turnover intention. Job stress directly has a positive and significant effect on turnover intention. Job satisfaction and work environment have a negative and significant effect on turnover intention through organizational commitment. Job stress has a positive and significant effect on turnover intention through organizational commitment.

Suggestion

Based on the conclusion, it can be suggested several things by BSSN in measuring the level of strategy with reducing the turnover intention for BSSN employees. The things that can be suggested are as follows:

a. BSSN can increase the organizational commitment of BSSN employees by increasing employee satisfaction. The BSSN in order to increase employee organizational commitment from the aspect of job satisfaction include forming a harmonious, communicative, and solid working relationship between BSSN employees by providing a gathering or team building program to all BSSN employees.

b. To reduce employee work stress in order to increase employee commitment to the organization, this can be done by coordinating and placing employees. According to the capacity and expertise of employees, giving appreciation or appreciation to BSSN employees who are performing well. So, some employees will feel appreciated for their work and to manage levels. Employee work stress should be given regular counseling for employees who have problems or obstacles in carrying out their work.

c. In order to improve an adequate work environment for employees so that organizational commitment can increase, BSSN can overcome this by upgrading some work facilities needed by employees, changing the paint color of workspace walls. There are dull with bright colors, controlling the cleanliness and tidiness of the workspace, cleaning the air vents to support any comfort of employees at work, implementing a harmonious work mechanism between employees, and superiors providing regular work directions and guidance to employees so that employees will be enthusiastic about working.

d. Strategic steps can be taken by BSSN to reduce the turnover rate of BSSN employees through increasing job satisfaction, including by providing compensation to employees based on their performance. So, some employees will felt satisfied and emotionally attached to BSSN. This also providing promotion at a faster rate for employees who excel in their performance (usually occurs for employees who have functional positions or employees who are entitled to special promotions) by still referring to the applicable regulations. Promotion and rank will lead to an increase in the basic salary received by employees, updating the mechanism regarding promotion and making standards / guidelines regarding career patterns by BSSN employees can be managed with properly according to their performance, making guidelines related to the mechanism for providing performance allowances. So, this provision of performance allowances based on the results were employee performance achievements, not only based on employee attendance in the office, but also employees can receive performance allowances on time and according to the amount, then it can improve some database to recapitulation of periodic salary increases (KGB) on BSSN PNS. The database can be made to be integrated with the Personnel Information System, which is more accurate and easy for monitoring by employees and the person in charge. These things will cause the employee's organizational commitment to increase so that the desire of BSSN employees to leave the organization (turnover intention) will also be minimized.

e. BSSN needs to develop a strategy to reduce employee turnover through efforts to reduce work stress by making work stress management mechanism guidelines or policies such as providing equal opportunities for all BSSN employees to get job guidance services.

f. Efforts to improve the work environment in reducing turnover rate of BSSN employees, which can be carried out with a consistency in the form of written policies to develop and update the work environment. So, BSSN employees can felt comfortable and safe at work, where this will increase the productivity or performance of BSSN employees.

g. To reduce the level of turnover intention, BSSN must be able to ensure that every employee has a strong organizational commitment by improving the mechanism for providing job satisfaction, paying attention to BSSN employees to be able to manage stress at work, and providing adequate facilities and work environment for BSSN employees.

h. In an effort to reduce the level of employee turnover intention through increasing organizational commitment, it is necessary to any policies and strategic steps in fulfilling aspects on employee job satisfaction by giving appreciation for high employee performance. For another reason, any contributing to the good name of BSSN

such as providing additional performance allowance incentives, giving take home pay. There is in accordance with the workload charged to employees, as well as award certificates to employees who excel and employees

i. An even distribution of workload according to employee competencies and to reduce employee stress levels in order to reduce employee turnover intention through increased organizational commitment. Where the division of work according to employee competencies and abilities will be able to encourage employee performance improvement. Guidance and direction for the work to be carried out from superiors to employees, which are also needed in determining work targets to be achieved, so that they will not exceeded by the predetermined target time and will minimize employee stress levels.

j. In an effort to reduce the level of employee turnover intention through increased organizational commitment, support from the aspect of an adequate work environment for BSSN employees, which is needed which encourages increased performance. BSSN needs to manage a comfortable work environment by providing a neat and clean work space by implementing the 5R system (Compact, Neat, Clean, Careful, Diligent) for employees. Renewal of work facilities and equipment such as laptops, personal computers, printers, and so on, like necessary to make it easier for employees to work. Creating a comfortable and up-to-date co-working space can also support employees to be more productive at work.

k. After being tested using the Structural Equational Model (SEM), the research model developed in this study is proven to strengthen theoretical concepts in the field of Human Resource Management. This concept can be a reference for other researchers who might be used with any development in the future, which is a research in the field of Human Resource Management. There are mutually sustainable and synergised for organizations in supporting the emphasis on turnover intention, so every vision and mission of the organization can be achieved.

l. This research is expected to be useful for the development of further knowledge in connection with some findings on research results, both in the form of further research, as well as for the development of science, especially Human Resource Management. Science development can applying for some new methods in other research to be added to this research. So, there will be applications of other sciences in the field of Human Resource Management, then pushed by some goals of management science itself.

m. For other researchers who want to continue research in the field of Human Resource Management, which is they will examine other variables and more real influence in the world of work. So, they will have a real picture and more cover the problems that are often encountered daily. In addition, the results of the conclusions and suggestions submitted will be more targeted, so they are expected to be good input for the organization going forwards.

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